
TIBETAN HATS IN MDO BA (DUOWA) PASTORAL COMMUNITY, REB GONG, A MDO, PR CHINA

Pad+ma rig 'dzin བསྐྱེད་ལོ་འཛིན། (Wanmerenzeng 完么仁增)*

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on hats and other apparel in a herding community (Mdo ba (Duowa) Town) in the east of Reb gong (Tongren City), Rma lho (Huangnan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. Locally worn hats, including their names, materials, where they were obtained, and the time of their popularity, were drawn from discussions with local culture bearers who shared their experiences and memories of what they had learned from their elders. Twelve photographs are included.

KEYWORDS

Traditional Tibetan hat; fox-fur hat; Tibet; lambskin hat; wool felt; Indian hat; Mdo ba (Duowa), Reb gong (Rebgong)

LOCAL PROVERBS

ཡ་རབས་མགོ་ཡི་ལྷ་ལོན་པ་ལས་མ་རབས་རྐང་གི་སྐྱམ་ལོན།

ya rabs mgo yi zhwa gon pa las ma rabs rkang gi lham khon

Wearing a bad man's shoes is better than wearing a nobleman's hat.

མགོ་ཡི་ལྷ་བཞིན་བྱུང།

mgo yi zhwa bzhin bkur

Respect them as much as their hat.

གཤམ་གྱི་ལྷ་ལོན་པ་ལས་མ་རབས་རྐང་གི་སྐྱམ་ལོན།

shAkya thub pa rig na zhwa mi phud/glang chen smyon pa thug na
lam mi phye

Seeing Gautama Buddha, he doesn't remove his hat; encountering
a mad elephant, he doesn't move away.

* Pad+ma rig 'dzin (Wanmerenzeng). 2023. Hats in an A mdo Pastoral Community, PR China. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:150-177.

མི་དཀར་དཀར་གྱི་མགོ་ལ་ལྷ་ནག་ནག་མ་སྟོན།

Mi dkar dkar gyi mgo la zhwa nag nag ma skon

Don't put a black hat on the head of a white person.

(Don't falsely accuse an innocent person.)

A full moon hung like a big drum in the eastern sky of our winter pasture on the fifteenth night of a chilly winter month in the year of the Wooden Pig (1995). Sister and I finished dinner quickly and rushed out into the milky night to a rectangular area between the yak pens of my family and a neighbor family where neighbor kids, Sister, and I played on moonlit nights. In the spring, elders grew *yu go* 'oats' (*Avena sativa L.*) here, harvested and dried it, and fed it to livestock in the early spring.

One after another, four boys and six girls – all neighbor kids – came where we waited. One girl was from a bit further away. She was the relative of one of our neighbors and was spending a night with them at their home. *Zhag 'dug* is the term we used for spending a night at a friend's home, a very exciting event during my childhood - the 1990s – partly because we learned new folktales and riddles. When one of my friends spent a night with my family, Father read *Pad+ma 'od 'bar*¹ for us before dinner. My friend was so obsessed with the tale that Father promised her to read the unfinished part the next time she visited.

After a long discussion, Sister and the other older kids chose two games. The first was the camel game that elders opposed because some children were easily frightened by the make-believe camel, and potentially dangerous tools like hoes were used in this game.

We prepared everything to play the camel game. Sister and two other children stood under a man's Tibetan robe turned inside-

¹ One of the great Tibetan hagiographies:

...it concerns a former life of Padmasambhava and takes place thousands of years ago in India, under the reign of a king hostile to Buddhism. The king imposes on the child ordeals thought to be unsurmountable from which he emerges victorious. He ends by overthrowing the king and establishes Buddhism in the kingdom <https://bit.ly/3em2311> 3 September 2022.

out. Sister held the long wooden handle of a hoe thrust straight up through one of the sleeves. Two pieces of light woolen cloth tied to the head of a hoe resembled camel eyes. A tall boy stood in the middle, and a girl stood beside him, representing the camel's humps. Suddenly, a gigantic 'live' camel appeared before the kids! As the camel moved around, we cheered in excitement, ran around the camel, and tried to touch it, but its hindleg - the girl at the end - kicked us away.

The second game was to dress a girl as a bride. Sister quickly came up with the idea of bringing the old fox-fur hat from the bottom of our black wooden box next to the altar in the upper part of our adobe house and covered by a yak skin. I never knew the date the fox hat was made nor to who it belonged. This *wa zhwa rwa 'dzig* 'fox-fur hat' (see below) had a horn-like tapered crown. Locals borrowed this hat occasionally for wedding ceremonies. My family kept the fox-fur hat in that wooden box at that time (the 1990s). Gradually, we lost its top metal ornament and, eventually, the fox hat itself. I searched for this hat but didn't find it when I went home last year.

Sister was the oldest and advised making up the "bride." She chose a girl and helped her put on the formal robe. Sister removed her earrings and told the "bride" to wear them. The "bride" also received three coral necklaces from the older female children. Girls prepared silver ornaments - *bzho bzung* and *glo mgo*¹ (see FIG 4) that women wore during their wedding ceremonies and other social gatherings such as horse races and Lo sar 'Tibetan New Year'.

After the "bride" wore the fox-fur hat and hung a white cloth over her face as a veil, she suddenly became a real bride. We solemnly went through rituals for each step of our imaginary wedding ceremony. A female child dressed as a boy joined the bridal party, and we sang folksongs and teased each other.

¹ Literary Tibetan: *glo gzar*. See <https://bit.ly/3cucgbr> 30 August 2022 for a short introduction to silver ornaments and an image.

INTRODUCTION

This article focuses on hats in a herding community east of Reb gong¹ (Tongren County), Mtso sngon Province, PR China. The names and materials of locally made hats and the creation process are described following consultations with local residents who shared their experiences and memories of what they had heard from their elders.

In the summer of 2022, young locals wore white wool-felt hats (FIG 11) similar to American Western cowboy hats, with slightly curved brims on both sides. Such hats are available via online shopping platforms such as Jingdong and Taobao under "Western Cowboy Hat in Tibetan Style" and "Tibetan New Style Hat."²

One of our eldest local elders, Gcod le (b. 1937), commented on changes in the local lifestyle and community attire since the late 1990s:

In the last few years, everything has been changing so rapidly. The clothing the young generation wear, the food we eat, and the machines we use daily are very strange to me. People tell me that youth wear clothes of different styles and colors. Even the Tibetan sash is a different color. In my time, we only had red sashes.

Recognizing these dramatic changes, I present this article as what can be studied and presented, recording additional information about traditional attire with the help of what aged elders remembered. This is important in creating a record of the past and provides a model for preserving local knowledge that is fast diminishing.

The *wa zhwa rwa 'dzig*³ 'horned fox-fur hat' is a traditional

¹ Officially: Thun rin, however, locals use "Reb gong."

² For popular new hats, see <https://bit.ly/3RkeJ6t> 30 September 2022.

³ My father (Chos ko, b. 1963) related a story about this hat he had heard in his childhood:

The special fox-fur hat was designed for Tibetan king Glang dar ma (reigned, 838-842) who had a horn on his head. He wore the horn-like-crown hat to hide this secret from the people of Tibet.

hat with a slightly backward and tapering crown with a bronze ornament on top and red ribbons hanging from the bottom of the top ornament. The crown is wool felt, and the top is covered with black fabric. The lower part is covered with red fabric. A round piece of fox fur that serves as the brim is adjacent to the red fabric. The hat's fox-fur part is folded when put on and unfolded when put away.

The *tsar zhwa* 'lambskin hat' is similar in shape to the horned fox-fur hat, but a piece of lambskin is used rather than fox-fur. Gcod le (b. 1937) described fox-fur and lambskin hats:

I only saw horned fox-fur hats in Mdo ba. In 1958, one of our Yo lag community members and I went to Zi ling to meet Tshe 'phags' father, who was imprisoned there, and escort him home. Later, he said, "I recognized the two-horned fox-fur hats you guys were wearing from far away, so I knew you were men from Mdo ba." He was skilled at designing and sewing this hat.

We usually bought cloth and other goods from Rong bo [Longwu].¹ Bla brang (Xiahe) was the nearest marketplace before 1958, but we rarely went there because of conflicts over stolen livestock and goods. The hat's metal ornament was available in Bla brang decades ago. Rich people wore this fox-fur hat in daily life during winter. Ordinary people wore it during Lo sar, horse races, other gatherings, and moving to a new pasture with their livestock. Lambskin hats were worn in summer. New brides and other female community members wore such hats while driving pack animals and livestock to new pastures. Once when we were moving from winter pasture to summer pasture, all the women wore lambskin hats and rode horses. I still remember that wonderful scene.

In my childhood (1990s), brides wore horned fox-fur hats during their wedding ceremonies. Later, women wore a fox-fur hat known as *rna drud* 'ear dragging' that originated in Bla brang, where such fox-fur hats were worn during Smon lam chen mo² 'the Great

¹ The location of Tongren City Town, which that locals refer to as "Rong bo."

² Tupden Jinpa (2019) suggests:

...between 1406 and the summer of 1408, Tsongkhapa first had the idea of hosting a grand prayer festival at the holy Jokhang Temple in Lhasa." ... It was held to honor the Buddha's performance of miracles at Śrāvastī in central India, which, according to the Tibetan calendar, occurred in the first

Prayer Festival', Lo sar, and weddings in winter. This woman's fox-fur hat grew in popularity in Mdo ba around 2000. Brocade covered the crown, the hat was trimmed with fox fur, and the tips of the ears drooped back.

Before this, women's fox-fur hat, the *wa to* 'cone-shaped fox-fur hat' (FIG 2), was popular. It had a higher crown of felt trimmed with fox fur. The higher crown was covered with brocade or *phrug khra*¹ 'colorful woolen cloth of various patterns'. The popularity of the 'ear-dragging' hat was such that the *wa to* gradually disappeared.

Rna drud is not a new hat name for locals because the fox-fur hat for men is known as *wa zhwa rna drud*, 'ear dragging fox-fur hat' (FIG 3). The male *rna drud* featured a brocade crown, and the fox-fur trim was larger than the women's 'ear dragging' hat. Also, its two ear tips drooped to the front, explaining the name. The inner part of the fox-fur trim was wool felt. A protruding stitch where the wool felt and fox skin were brought together at the bottom of the fox fur trim was covered by red cloth, adding to its attractiveness.

Locals banned precious skins and fur apparel in 2006 (Lobsang Yongdan 2018). Afterward, no locals wore fox-fur hats in Mdo ba, even during wedding ceremonies. In recent wedding ceremonies (~2022), brides wore lambskin hats with a crown cover of various fabrics and brocades of different colors from the top to the lower part of the crown (FIG 1).

month of the year.

'Jigs med theg mchog (1988:134) writes that [The grand prayer festival [in Reb gong] began in the year of the Water Dog (1742) after the Second Skyabs mgon [Ngag dbang 'phrin las rgya mtsho (b. 1678-1739)] 'Great Religious Leader of Reb gong'.

¹ In the 1990s or earlier, locals cut colored woolen cloth into thin narrow strips (<https://bit.ly/3pA11B7> 6 September 2022) to trim Tibetan robes. Locals distinguish *phrug rdo phrug* and *phrug 'o rta* according to patterns. *Phrug* 'sheep wool cloth' is alternatively known as *snam bu* [Ch, *pulu*]. *Rdo phrug* (<https://bit.ly/3dLCXIO> 22 August 2022) features alternate strips colored red, yellow, green, brown, blue, etc. (see the robe trim in FIGS 2 & 6). For *phrug 'o rta* ('*o rta* 'churning stick') robe trim (see FIG 4), see <https://bit.ly/3CjvF9l> and <https://bit.ly/3T72IDG> 22 August 2022.

The most traditional hat is the *phying zhwa* 'Tibetan felt hat' that locals wear daily. Made of wool felt, there are at least two types. One is locally known as *phying zhwa mgo ring* 'long-headed [crown] felt hat' (FIG 7). Locals no longer make this felt hat, but local children wear it during Lo sar and other social gatherings. The long-headed felt hat is available in the markets of Reb gong. Karma smon lam and Skal bzang nor bu (2005:9) describe the *phying zhwa rtse ring* 'long headed [crown] felt hat' as a summer hat for the Reb gong people.

The second type has a brim similar to the Indian felt hat. A senior local monk recalled:

When I herded calves at the start of the summer season, some community members tried to make a wool felt hat using a large mortar to make wool felt into the crown and create the shape of a *rgya zhwa* 'Indian hat', but the Indian felt hat is more beautiful and better quality than this homemade felt hat.

Karma smon lam and Skal bzang nor bu (2005:12) describe Indian felt hats:

Rgya gar zhwa mo 'Indian hat' is made of felt and its shape and quality are more beautiful and better than Tibetan felt hats. ...the [Indian] hat was brought at the very beginning by Tibetan business people [into Tibet], and because of that, the hat was known as *Rgya gar zhwa mo*. However, in other Tibetan areas, like Gtsang, the felt hat was colloquially known as *phing zhwa* or *phyi zhwa* 'foreign hat' because [locals] saw foreigners wearing the Indian felt hat.

*Rgya zhwa*¹ is a short form for *rgya gar zhwa mo* 'Indian hat'. Locals use *rgya zhwa*, *rgya zhwa li mo*, and *rgya gar li mo* alternatively to refer to the Indian hat. Of note is the use of *gya gar*, a Tibetan term for India, while *li mo* is phonetically a Chinese word in Tibetan, referring to a sort of top hat.² The combination of these two terms translates as "Indian hat." Some community elders said the Indian felt hat was locally popular before 1949.

¹ Some online dictionaries mistakenly translate "*rgya zhwa*" as 'Chinese cap'.

² See *li mo* at <https://bit.ly/3rfKEUq> 30 September 2022.

In the 1990s, local young women wore Indian felt hats with plastic flowers during horse races and other summer social gatherings. Young men wore Indian felt hats without flowers. Young people wore new hats for social gatherings, while elders kept their old hats for years.

My father went to Zi ling (Xining), the capital of Mtsho sngon Province, in 1995 and returned home with a big box of Indian felt hats he sold to locals except one for my sister (b. 1984). It was spring, so we had not yet moved to the summer pasture. Locals bought hats for summer when they would participate in social gatherings. The hats protected their faces from intense mid-summer sunlight on the high Plateau.

Around 2010, a brown felt hat was popular among locals, particularly women. This hat and a white felt hat, similar in style that became popular in 2015, were locally placed in the *rgya zhwa* (FIGS 9&10) category. These hats were available in Thun rin (Tongren) markets and Bsang chu (Xiahe) County Town. Local shop owners sold them periodically in Mdo ba Town. Gradually, locals began wearing wool felt hats of different colors and styles.

FIG 1. Dkar mo (b. 2004) wears a lambskin hat and other wedding apparel at her home in Mdo ba Town (2021, unidentified photographer). She wears a *tsha ru* 'lambskin robe' with a coral inlaid silver belt, a pair of gold earrings, and a gold necklace.

FIG 2. A *wa to* worn by Rta mgrin skyid (b. 1950) (Thun rin City Town, 1993, unidentified studio photographer). She wears a pair of silver earrings and necklaces, including at least one string of coral.

FIG 3. *Wa zhwa rna drud'* ear dragging fox-fur hat'. Rig' dzin rdo rje (b. 1968) (winter pasture Khug rgan, Mdo ba Town, 1994, Rin chen don 'grub). Rifles were popular among local herders. Community elders suggested the first rifle local herders used may have been the *me mda'* 'Tibetan musket', locally known as *sman bo'u* 'powder rifle'.¹ The rifle in this photo was a .22 Long Rifle (LR), locally known as *phyi bo'u* 'marmot rifle'.² As a child, I saw my brother (Rin chen don 'grub, b. 1981) and his herding companions kill a marmot with a .22 LR. Local herders began concealing their rifles in the late 1990s and early 2000s. By about 2015, the government had confiscated all local private and community rifles.

¹ *Sman* 'medicine' refers to gunpowder.

² Locals also use the Chinese name *xiaokou qiang* 'small barrel rifle'. For more, see <https://bit.ly/3RTWbLb> 11 September 2022.

FIG 4. *Wa to* and *wa zhwa rna drud* worn by (L) 'Jigs byed 'tsho (b. 1973) and (R) Lcags thar skyid (b. 1970; with her son, Lha mchog rdo rje (b. 1996) (Reb gong Town, 1999, unidentified studio photographer). 'Jigs byed 'tsho wears a *glo mgo* 'side silver ornament¹ on her right. Both women wear *skag rdo/skag bsdoms* 'belt' *bzho bzung* 'milk hooks' on their left. Both wear *tsha ru* 'lambskin robe', formal winter attire. The robes worn in FIGS 2 & 4 were designed before 2000. Afterward, most women's robes resemble the robes in FIGS 5 & 6. Note the difference in the upper trim² on the robes. 'Jigs byed 'tsho's robe features *phrug gseg 'dra* 'tilted trim', popular among younger people. Lha mchog rdo rje wears a *phyag mdud* 'sacred knot' likely given by a respected religious figure. The center of the red cloth strip features a small *sku* that, in this case, is a small metal Buddha image worn to protect against evil.

¹ Local women no longer wear such side silver ornaments.

² Robe trim is generally known as *phrug khra*.

FIG 5. *Wa zhwa rna drud* worn by (L) Gzung's 'dus 'tsho (b. 1984) and (R) Chos ko (b. 1975) (Reb gong Town, 2006, unidentified studio photographer). Both women wear *tsha ru* 'lamb skin robes', several strings of coral, silver earrings, and silver belts. Coral necklaces and silver/gold necklaces and earrings were locally banned after 2006, but around 2015, local women gradually resumed wearing gold and silver necklaces and *rna tog* 'earrings' and silver belts. Chos ko wears a coral inlaid *dngul gyi ga'u* 'silver amulet'. Such amulets often contain sacred objects such as *mdud pa* 'knots' given by religious figures, medicines in the form of *za yig* 'eating letters' that might be paper with illness-curing mantras to cure illness, a piece of cloth from a religious figure's *gzan* 'kasaya', and so on.

FIG 6. *Wa zhwa rna drud* and *po de rna bzhi* 'four eared hat' worn by (L) Gzung 'dus 'tsho (b. 1984) and (R) Gcod pa 'tsho (b.1994) (Reb gong Town, 2006, unidentified studio photographer). Gzung 'dus 'tsho wears a *tsha ru* 'lamb skin robe' trimmed with *sram* 'otter fur', a silver belt, several coral necklaces, and silver earrings. Gcod pa 'tsho wears a blue *pang khebs* 'apron' trimmed with *rdo phrug* with her *sru tshar* 'haired robe' also trimmed with *rdo phrug*. She also wears a *Po de rna bzhi* or *zhwa mo tshe ring skyin khebs* 'long-life hat'. Karma smon lam and Skal bzang nor bu (2005:7) describe this as a winter hat for the people of the Lha sa region. Some Mdo ba locals wore this hat before 1949, which became popular again among young Mdo ba people in the 2000s.

FIG 7. This modern 'long headed felt hat', locally known as *phying zhwa mgo ring*, is worn by 'Jigs med bsam 'grub (b. 2012) as he holds his birthday cake at his family's house in Mdo ba Township Town (2022, Gcod pa 'tsho). Senior villagers said the locally made felt hat approximates the style of this modern felt hat and added that more recently (in the 2020s), felt hats were made in Rtse khog (Zeku County) and other Tibetan areas. Both the collar and the ends of the sleeves of the robe worn by 'Jigs med bsam 'grub are brocade-lined, a recent trend.

Locals historically celebrated birthdays at three and, if a person lived long enough, at eighty, ninety, and one hundred. However, beginning in about 2013, young parents began purchasing birthday cakes from Thun rin City for their kids' birthdays.¹ 'Jigs med bsam 'grub's mother asked a local villager to buy a birthday cake (seventy-two RMB) and bring it to 'Jigs med bsam 'grub's home in his private car.

¹ See, for example, Lhun 'grub's description (Lhun 'grub et al. 2021) of his wife's relative's birthday party in 2015:

The little girl was wearing a Tibetanized shirt, blue-gray jeans, a birthday hat, and shyly blowing out the sparking candles stuck on the birthday cake. Some of her friends sang "Happy Birthday" in Chinese (207).

Lhun 'grub goes on to comment:

The difference between those my age and those about ten years younger is enormous in terms of many fundamental aspects of life, including food, celebrations, clothing, recreation, and conversation topics (207).

FIG 8. (L) Lcags sgron (b. 1989) and (R) Gcod pa (b. 1990) wear the *rgya zhwa* 'Indian hat' with plastic flowers during a local beauty pageant (Mdo ba Town, 2003, unidentified photographer). Flowers in hats worn by women were common in Mtsho sngon.¹ Both robes are trimmed in otter fur. The upper trim of Gcod pa's robe is *gzig* 'leopard skin'. Some locals used imitation animal fur trims on their robes, but this practice gradually stopped.

¹ See, for example, flowers in the hats of Mongghul (Tu) women in Huzhu Mongghul (Tu) Autonomous County (Limusishiden et al. (2014:161, 174, 184 dating to as early as 1984).

FIG 9. A *rgya zhwa* worn by Bsod noms tshe ring (b. 1987) in a Kha skya field of *me tog ser chen* 'marsh marigold' (*Caltha palustris* L.) (Mdo ba Town, 2021, 'Brug dkar tshe ring).

FIG 10. *Rgya zhwa* hats worn at a horse race in Mdo ba Town by (L-R) Skal bzang rdo rje (b. 1993; *phrug lwa* or *phrug* 'woolen cloth' robe), Ting 'dzin skyabs (b. 2000; *ras lwa* 'thin-cloth robe'), Rdo rje tshe brtan (b. 2000; *ras lwa* 'thin-cloth robe'), and 'Jigs byed skyabs (b. 1998; *rtsag pa* 'sheep skin robe'). (2021, unidentified photographer).

FIG 11. Newly popular *rgya zhwa* hats worn by (L-R) Rna me 'tsho (b. 1996), Rta mgrin 'tsho (b. 1993), and Sgron dkar skyid (b. 2001), models for a local Tibetan robe company that designs and sells shoes, clothes, and other products. Rin chen bkra shis (b. 1996), a local herdsman, opened it in 2020. The company's logo is in the upper right-hand corner (Mdo ba Town, 2021, Rin chen bkra' shis). The face masks were because of COVID concerns.

FIG 12. A Mdo ba shop operated by Rin chen bkra shis (b. 1996) and his wife sells in-store and online products. They plan to expand the shop and increase product selection in December 2022 (Jo yag gyon chas tshad yod spyi gnyer khang 'Joyak Clothing Limited Company' in Mdo ba Township Town, 2022, Rin chen bkra' shis).

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<https://bit.ly/3OBrt8u> 30 June 2022

lo sar ལོ་སར།
 Lobsang Yongdan, blo bzang
 yon tan ལྷོ་བཟང་ཡོན་ཏན།
 mdo ba མདོ་བ།
 mdud pa མདུད་པ།
 me tog ser chen མེ་ཏོག་སེར་ཆེན།
 mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྒྲོན།
 pad+ma 'od 'bar བསྐྱེད་འདུལ་བར།
 pad+ma rig 'dzin བསྐྱེད་རིག་འཛིན།
 Padmasambhava, pad+ma
 'byung gnas བསྐྱེད་འབྱུང་གནས།
 pang khebs བང་ཁེབས།
 phing zhwa ཕིང་ཟླ།
 phrug 'o rta ཕུག་འོ་རྟ།
 phrug gseg 'dra ཕུག་གསེག་འདྲ།
 phrug khra ཕུག་ཁ།
 phrug lwa ཕུག་ལ།
 phyag mdud ཕྱག་མདུད།
 phyi bo'u ཕྱི་བོ་འུ།
 phyi zhwa ཕྱི་ཟླ།
 phying zhwa mgo ring
 ཕྱིང་ཟླ་མགོ་རིང་།
 phying zhwa rtse ring
 ཕྱིང་ཟླ་རྩེ་རིང་།
 phying zhwa ཕྱིང་ཟླ།
 po de rna bzhi པོ་དེ་རྣ་བཞི།
 ras lwa རས་ལ།
 rdo phrug རྫོ་ཕུག
 rdo rje tshe brtan རྫོ་རྩེ་ཚོ་བརྟན།
 rebgong, reb gong རེབ་གོང་།
 rgya gar li mo རྒྱ་གར་ལི་མོ།
 rgya gar zhwa mo རྒྱ་གར་ལྷ་མོ།
 rgya zhwa རྒྱ་ཟླ།
 rgya zhwa li mo རྒྱ་ཟླ་ལི་མོ།
 rig 'dzin rdo rje རིག་འཛིན་རྫོ་རྩེ།
 rin chen bkra' shis
 རིན་ཆེན་བརྟ་ཤེས།

rin chen don 'grub
 རིན་ཆེན་དོན་འགྲུབ།
 rma lho ར་ལྷོ།
 rna drud རྣ་བུད།
 rna me 'tsho རྣ་མེ་འཚོ།
 rna tog རྣ་ཏོག།
 rong bo རོང་བོ།
 rta mgrin 'tsho རྟ་མགིན་འཚོ།
 rta mgrin skyid རྟ་མགིན་སྦྱིད།
 rtsag pa རྟག་པ།
 sgron dkar skyid སྒྲོན་དཀར་སྦྱིད།
 skal bzang nor bu
 སྐལ་བཟང་ནོར་བུ།
 skag rdo, skag bsdoms
 སྐག་རྫོ་ཡང་ན་སྐག་བསྐྱེས།
 skal bzang rdo rje
 སྐལ་བཟང་རྫོ་རྩེ།
 sku སྐུ།
 skyabs mgon སྐབས་མགོན།
 smon lam chen mo
 སྦོན་ལམ་ཆེན་མོ།
 sram སྐམ།
 sru tshar སྐུ་ཚར།
 thun rin སུན་རིན།
 ting 'dzin skyabs ཉིང་འཛིན་སྐབས།
 tsar zhwa ཚར་ཟླ།
 tsha ru ཚ་རུ།
 tshe 'phags ཚོ་འཕགས།
 Tsongkhapa, rje tsong kha ba
 རྩེ་ཚོང་ཁ་བ།
 Tupden Jinpa, thub bstan
 sbyin pa ཐུབ་བསྐྱེན་སྦྱིན་པ།
 wa to ལ་ཏོ།
 wa zhwa rna drud ལ་ཟླ་རྣ་བུད།
 wa zhwa rwa 'dzig ལ་ཟླ་ར་འཛིན།
 yo lag ཡོ་ལག།
 yu go ཡུ་གོ།

za yig ཟ་ཡིག

zhag 'dug ཞག་འདུག

zi ling ཟེ་ལིང་།

CHINESE TERMS

Duowa 多哇

Huangnan 黄南

Huzhu 互助

Jingdong 京东

Longwu 隆务

pulu 穉穉

Qinghai 青海

Taobao 淘宝

Tongren 同仁

Tu 土

Wanmerenzeng 完么仁增

Xiahe 夏河

Xiaokou qiang 小口枪

Xining 西宁

Zeku 泽